

ISic1179

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

stone

Object

fragmentary

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-07-09 - Jonathan Prag revised the file based on study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Recorded as beside the great door in the front of the Church of S. Maria dei Palazzi by Gualtherus, 1621-1624, and subsequently by Castelli, Principe di Torremuzza, who notes that it was dug up from the ruins of Halaesa.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, lost

Physical Description

Castelli, Principe di Torremuzza (1753: 147) notes that the stone was damaged on all sides

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Remains to two lines of Greek letters, damaged at both ends (?)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Gualtherus records the sigmas in line 2 and the epsilon in line 1 as lunate (and he is followed by Castelli)

Letter heights:

Line 1: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. [---]IMN[]YATONΔEΠOIKIΛ[---]

2. [---]IXIII[]ΣΟΥΣΑΠΑΝΤΟΣΚΙ[---]

Apparatus

Text after Gualtherus and Castelli

Translation

Commentary

Gualtherus records the sigmas in line 2 and the epsilon in line 1 as lunate (and

he is followed by Castelli) and, assuming that this is an accurate record of what he saw, suggests a date of the imperial or late antique period. Kaibel speculated that it might be a verse text of the Byzantine period, reading τόνδε ποικίλ[ον] at the end of line 1, but despaired of interpretation. In similar vein, if correct, [-]υατον could be the end of a transliterated Latin name such as Torquatus, but the difficulty is that it is entirely possible that some of the letters are wrongly transcribed.

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DEPERDITÆ. ET. QUÆ. OB. ABSENTIAM
dominorum, aut alia obstacula aspici non potuerit

In ade Grefali. terra abilita

294

D. SEMPRONIO
P. L. PRIMIONI
ANNORVM. XVIII

In via d. Lucie. apud Ant. Marchesium.
calce abilitata

295

MAXIMO
IACONO
ET. N. Z

Maximus
Iasonis P.
annorum LX

In maiori templo
297 STHENII AEDES

Legit Alph. Zappata veteram ma-
ximam. et. in. intelligit

CEPHALOEDIS

Ad portam Piscariam. In. forma

296

ΣΘΣΙΝΥΜΒΟΝ
ΚΡΑΦΑΤΕΚΑΙΡΕ

Sisymbon
Crapate salus

D. MARIA. DE. PALATIO. seu. DE. PALATI
II. lapide à Thosa, opido Fran. Vicinillia Marchionis Hieracij

Secus portam magnam in pariete

297
[IMN. . . TATONA & DOXIA]
[EXIII. . . COYCAPIANTOCKI]

299
IMP. CAESAREI
DIVI F
AVGVSTO PO.
MVNICIPIVM

Prope gradus, quibus ad aram maiorem athen-
dicitur in marmoreis. in hoc parte

298
GEOΣ ΠΑΞΙ
ΑΔΑΜΟΣ ΤΟΝ ΑΑΑΙΝΟΝ
ΙΟΥΣΙΝΗΝ ΔΙΟΥΣΙΝΟΣ
ΑΑΙΘΟΝΑ
ΝΕΠΤΕΛΙΑΣ . ΕΝΙΚΕΝ

Dico simul
populus H. al. gherum
Augustus Dionis P.
Lapideum
Inventoria causa

Copy of Gualtherus 1624 no.297 (from Arachne edition)